

intensified and that regional rice improvement programs expand the genetic diversity of their breeding materials. The need for more training of rice scientists and for additional support to national rice research programs was evident to the group.

Below is a list of participants in IRTP monitoring tours during 1977.

1. *Arid regions tour* (Sudan, Egypt, and Pakistan)
 - G. Ghobrial, Sudan
 - M. S. Bald, Egypt

- M. Moafizad, Iran
- A. M. Farkhonde, Iran
- G. McLean, Ford Foundation, Egypt
- M. Rosero, CIAT/IRRI, Colombia
- W. R. Coffman, IRRI
- H. E. Kauffman, IRRI

2. *Nepal and northern India tour*

- A. N. M. R. Karim, Bangladesh
- M. Nasiruddin, Bangladesh
- H. K. Pande, India
- D. N. Borthakur, India
- G. Verma, India
- S. Saran, India

- B. B. Shahi, Nepal
- K. P. Shreshta, Nepal
- D. V. Seshu, IRRI
- J. C. O'Toole, IRRI

3. *Central America and Mexico tour*

- J. I. Murillo, Costa Rica
- W. R. Pazos, Guatemala
- L. H. Aragon, Mexico
- E. Espinosa, Panama
- M. Rosero, CIAT/IRRI, Colombia
- S. K. De Datta, IRRI
- D. V. Seshu, IRRI
- H. E. Kauffman, IRRI

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Potash nutrition and sheath blight disease

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The effect of potash application on the development of sheath blight, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, was investigated in a pot-culture experiment during the 1976 wet season (June–September) with ADT 31 used as the susceptible rice variety. Muriate of potash as basal

dressing was applied at 0,49,99, 148, 198, and 247 kg K₂O/ha (converted from kg/acre). Nitrogen at 123 kg/ha was applied as urea and phosphorus at 62 kg P₂O₅/ha as superphosphate to all treatments. Disease intensity and yield were recorded.

Potassium application reduced the disease incidence significantly. As the potash levels increased, the disease incidence decreased, with a corresponding increase in yield (see table). Investigation reveals that potash nutrition gives rice resistance to sheath blight.

Sapporo, where natural occurrence of ragged stunt had not been observed.

Of 40 insects that received the supernate injection, 21 survived for 2 weeks afterward. They were used to inoculate seedlings of the rice variety Mihonishiki, at 3 insects/seedling for an inoculation feeding period of 3 days. The same insects were then transferred to inoculate another set of seedlings for 3 days. All 14 inoculated seedlings developed symptoms of the disease.

In addition to supporting the viral nature of ragged stunt, the experiment showed that the injection method can be used in bioassay of the virus.

Effect of potash on the incidence of sheath blight disease. Tamil Nadu, India.

Potash level (kg K ₂ O/ha)	Mean disease index	Decrease in disease over control (%)	Mean grain yield (g/pot)	Increase in yield over control (%)
0	81	–	11	–
49	76	6	11	6
99	65	20	12	15
148	61	24	14	26
198	55	33	15	42
247	49	39	16	50

C.D. (P = 0.01)

Bioassay of rice ragged stunt virus

T. Senboku and E. Shibata, University of Hokkaido, Sapporo, Japan; and E. R. Tiongo and K. C. Ling, International Rice Research Institute

The infectivity of rice ragged stunt virus was determined by the injection method

at the University of Hokkaido, Japan. Fresh leaves of diseased plants of IR3839-1, infected in the Philippines, were macerated in a buffer solution and centrifuged. The supernate was injected by a fine glass capillary into the body of brown planthoppers *Nilaparvata lugens*. The insects had been reared for years in

Ragged stunt disease in Thailand

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Ragged stunt disease, transmitted by *Nilaparvata lugens*, was first noted in Thailand by Dr. E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI entomologist, during an October 1977 visit to the Bangkhen and Rangsit Rice Experiment Stations. It caused serious yield losses in the variety RD7 around Bangkok at the end of the 1977 wet season. About 3,200 ha of RD7 in Chachengsao province, central plains region, were severely infected; in many